

Past and Present Scholarship on The *Politeia* of the Epirotes and a New Book on the History of Molossia

Jessica Piccinini

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The term “Epirus” is used by ancient sources and modern scholars to mean both a region at the fringes of the ancient Greek world and a political unity of the tribes living there.¹ From a geographical standpoint, the region, nowadays lying between North-Western Greece and Albania, got its name from the Greek word ἡπειρος –often appearing in its Western Greek form with initial alpha, *apeiros*–, meaning “the mainland”, according to the maritime perspective of the colonists approaching land from the sea and the island of Corcyra.² ἡ ἡπειρος acquired a toponymic value in the archaic and classical period,³ designating a specific part of the broad region of North-Western Greece, whose Northern limits, separating the Greek mainland from barbarian Illyria, were traced with difficulty.

The term “Epirus” in the sense of a unified state developed much later, in the last decades of the 3rd century BC with the creation of the *koinon* of the Epirotes.⁴ Until that moment the region was politically very fragmentary: the *poleis* of the coast, Euboean and Corinthian colonies, lived next to tribes organized into different and independent *ethne*.⁵ The actual geomorphic condition of the Epirote landscape, with mountains occupying eighty-eight per cent of the whole region,⁶ and its small, unevenly distributed population conditioned both the political organization and the socio-economic system.⁷ In such a context –a large territory, plains confined to the

¹ XEN., *Hell.* VI, 1, 7; EPHOR., *FGrHist* 70 F 129b; LYCURG., 1, 26; DIOD., XIX, 36 and 88; *IG IV*² 195. 23, 73, 122. 60.

² P. FUNKE, N. MOUSTAKIS & B. HOCHSCHULZ, “Epeiros”, in M.H. HANSEN & T.H. NIELSEN (eds), *An Inventory of Archaic and Classical Poleis*, Oxford, 2004, p. 339; I. MALKIN, “Greek Ambiguities: ‘Ancient Hellas’ and ‘Barbarian Epirus’”, in I. MALKIN (ed.), *Ancient Perceptions of Greek Ethnicity*, Cambridge Mass., 2001, p. 188-191.

³ XEN., *Hell.* VI, 1, 7; EPHOR., *FGrHist* 70 F 129b; LYCURG., 1, 26; *IG IV*² 195. 23, 73, 122. 60.

⁴ P. CABANES, *L'Épire de la mort de Pyrrhos à la conquête romaine (272-167 av. J.-C.)*, Paris, 1976, p. 546-547 no. 15.

⁵ M.H. HANSEN, “Introduction. Ethnic as Evidence for Polis Identity”, in M.H. HANSEN & T.H. NIELSEN (eds), *op. cit.*, p. 46-47.

⁶ S.I. DAKARIS, “Epiro e Magna Grecia fino all’età arcaica”, in *Magna Grecia Epiro e Macedonia. Atti del ventiquattresimo convegno di studi sulla Magna Grecia, Taranto, 5-10 ottobre 1984*, Taranto, 1985, p. 103-104.

⁷ N.G.L. HAMMOND, “Physical Features and Historical Geography”, in M.B. SAKELLARIOU (ed.), *Epirus, 4000 Years of Greek History and Civilization*, Athens, 1997, p. 26.

coast and river courses, population scattered in small settlements– the socio-political organizational structure of the *ethnos* fitted perfectly.⁸

Ancient sources inform us that the territory and people were essentially divided into three main groups, –the Molossians, the Chaonians and the Thesprotians–,⁹ who in the early period “lived in unfortified villages” rather than in cities – *οἰκοῦν δὲ κατὰ κώμας ἀτειχίστους*.¹⁰ In the last decades of the 5th century BC the Molossians, but not the Chaonians or the Thesprotians, at least according to Thucydides, were ruled by a monarch.¹¹

The political interrelationships of these Epirote *ethne* from the 5th to the 3rd century, and the nature of their *politeia(i)* have produced a lively debate since the very first years of the 20th century. As literary evidence concerning Epirus is altogether scant, especially in respect of constitutional matters,¹² the debate on Epirote *politeia(i)* was nourished by the progressive discovery of inscriptions and coins, hinting at the political development of Epirus between the 5th and the 3rd centuries BC. They were found mainly, but not exclusively, during the archaeological excavations at Dodona.¹³

⁸ As for the prevalence of *ethne* in ancient Northern Greece, see M. SORDI, “La Grecia degli *ethne*: genti e regioni settentrionali e centrali”, in S. SETTIS (a cura di), *I Greci, II, 2*, Torino, 1997, p. 87-108; R. BROCK & S. HODKINSON, “Introduction: An Alternative to the Democratic Polis”, in R. BROCK & S. HODKINSON (eds.), *Alternatives to Athens. Varieties of Political Organization and Community in Ancient Greece*, Oxford, 2000, p. 21-30; C. MORGAN, *Early Greek States Beyond the Polis*, London/New York, 2003, esp. p. 4-16.

⁹ Evidence testifies to the presence of minor *ethne* too, such as the Athamanes, the Bylliones, the Antitanes, etc.

¹⁰ THUC., III, 94, 4; PS.-SCYLAX, 28-32; STRABO, VII, 7, 5. S.C. BAKHUIZEN, “The Continent and the Sea: Notes on Greek Activities in Ionic and Adriatic Waters”, in P. CABANES (éd.), *L’Illyrie méridionale et l’Épire dans l’Antiquité. Actes du colloque international de Clermont-Ferrand (22-25 octobre 1984)*, Clermont-Ferrand, 1987, p. 185.

¹¹ THUC., II, 80, 5-6. It is difficult, however, to go further and establish, for instance, whether the Antitanes, whom Thucydides mentions as, at that moment, in coalition with the Molossians, were also politically incorporated into the Molossian kingdom, as a consequence of a possible Molossian expansionism, or whether they were allies only because of the war.

¹² Besides THUC., II, 80, 5-6; III, 94, 4; THEOPOM., *FGrHist* 115 F 382 (= STRABO, VII, 7, 5); PLUT., *Pyrrh.* V, 5; DIOD., XIX, 36 and 88, Aristotle wrote an Epirote constitution too, but only a tiny fragment –the title and the mention of the Amyntai, an *ethnos* of the Thesprotians– survives (ARISTOT., fr. 494 Rose, in STEPH. BYZ., s.v. Ἀμύνται - ἔθνος Θεσπρωτικόν. μένος πλείοντες Ἀμύνται. καὶ Ἀριστοτέλης ἐν τῇ τῶν Ἡπειρωτῶν πολιτείᾳ). Molossians were also mentioned in ARISTOT., *Pol.*, 1310 b 34 – 40 and *Pol.*, 1313 a 23 – 30 as mere examples, respectively, of how benefactors of communities can become kings and how less powerful and less despotic monarchs endure longer than others. See a full discussion of Aristotle’s perspective on the Molossians in J.K. DAVIES, “A Wholly Non-Aristotelian Universe: The Molossians as *Ethnos*, State, and Monarchy”, in R. BROCK & S. HODKINSON (eds.), *Alternatives to Athens. Varieties of Political Organization and Community in Ancient Greece*, Oxford, 2000, p. 237-239.

¹³ Important evidence, not from Dodona, is to be found, for instance, in the *theorodokoi* lists of Epidauros and Argos. *IG IV*² 1, 95 and *SEG LVIII*, 321; see, P. PERLMAN, *City and*

The epigraphic and numismatic evidence brought to light during the archaeological excavations in the sanctuary of Zeus Naios and Dione in the 1930s,¹⁴ significantly boosted research on the Epirote constitution after the first pioneering works by M.P. Nilsson, C. Klotzsch and G.N. Cross.¹⁵ Some of the new data, namely honorary decrees, manumission acts and coins –important in the study of *politeia(i)* because of their formulae and lexicon¹⁶– were published by D. Evangelides.¹⁷ However, a proper discussion arose only after the works of P.R. Franke, who identified coin issues with the legend “of the Molossians” and “of the Epirotes” and dated numismatic evidence on historical, rather than on stratigraphic, grounds to the second and the third quarter of the 4th century BC respectively.¹⁸ As a consequence, he postulated that the Epirote *symmachia* was founded already in c. 329-325 BC as a result of Olympias’ machinations and that it was a loose confederacy under Molossian domination.¹⁹ The book caused a strong reaction from one of the major experts on the Hellenistic history of Epirus, P. Lévêque,²⁰ who accused the “young” Franke of ignoring some of the new epigraphic documents, i.e. the above-mentioned proxeny and manumission decrees discovered by Evangelides; according to Lévêque the inclusion of these documents would have built a more convincing picture in support of Epirote federalism.²¹

Sanctuary in Ancient Greece: The Theorodokia in the Peloponnese, Göttingen, 2000, p. 31, 67-87 and 100-104; DAVIES, *art. cit.*, p. 248 D5; M. MELFI & J. PICCININI, “Le fonti”, in R. PERNA & Dh. ÇONDI (a cura di), *Hadrianopolis II. Risultati delle indagini archeologiche 2005-2010*, Bari, 2012, p. 54 nos. 6-7.

¹⁴ D. EVANGELIDES, “Ἡπειρωτικά ἐρευναί. 1. Ἡ ἀνασκαφή τῆς Δωδωνῆς”, *Epeirotika Chronika* X (1935), p. 192-264.

¹⁵ M.P. NILSSON, *Studien zur Geschichte des alten Epeiros*, Lund, 1909; C. KLOTZSCH, *Epeirotische Geschichte bis zum Jahre 280 v. Chr.*, Berlin, 1911; G.N. CROSS, *Epirus, A Study in Greek Constitutional Development*, Cambridge, 1932. In the same year Accame published an article on the diarchy of the Molossians (S. ACCAME, “La diarchia dei Molossi”, *RIFC* LXIV [1932], p. 522-534).

¹⁶ Fundamental in this sense is the mention of magistrates (*ieromnamones*, *damiourgoi*, *synarchontes*) in association with ethnics, which vary in number, of collective terms, such as *koinon* and *symmachia/symmachoi*, and of eponyms (Molossian kings, *prostates* and *grammateoi*). On these offices in Epirus, see T. CORSTEN, *Von Stamm zum Bund, Gründungen und territoriale Organisation griechischer Bundestaaten*, München, 1999, p. 201-202

¹⁷ D. EVANGELIDES, “Ψήφισμα τοῦ βασιλέως Νεοπτολέμου ἐκ Δωδώνης”, *AE* (1956), p. 1-13.

¹⁸ P. R. FRANKE, *Alt-Epirus und das Königtum der Molosser*, Kallmünz, 1955, p. 3-30; P. R. FRANKE, *Die antiken Münzen von Epirus, I-II*, Wiesbaden, 1961.

¹⁹ FRANKE, *Alt-Epirus cit.*, esp. p. 55-78.

²⁰ P. LÉVÊQUE, *Pyrrhos*, Paris, 1957.

²¹ P. LÉVÊQUE, “Recherches nouvelles sur l’histoire de l’Épire”, *REG* LXX (1957), p. 495-498 and L. BREGLIA, “Le emissioni dei Molossi e di Alessandro il Neottolero per la storia politica dell’Epiro”, *AIIN* IV (1957), p. 224-229 on the political history of Epirus through the analysis of the numismatic evidence.

Almost a decade later, N.G.L. Hammond contributed to the debate by drawing attention to a few unpublished documents.²² His work on Epirus, which in nature was half way between the research of an antiquarian and the elaboration of a modern historian, is the product of three decades of travel and research in southern Albania and North-Western Greece. District by district Hammond made surveys and collected literary, archaeological, epigraphic and numismatic evidence for a physical, economic and political description of the area. As for the constitution of the Epirote tribes and *ethne*, he argues that the idea of Epirote federalism should be altogether rejected. He utterly seized on the literal meaning of the word *symmachia*, claiming the existence of a long-lasting alliance between all the Epirote *ethne*.²³

A proper collection of documents, a few of which were being published for the first time, was made in the 70s by P. Cabanes.²⁴ Besides gathering all the available evidence and providing comments and translations, Cabanes dated the inscriptions, mostly on historical grounds. This collection has constituted the foundation on which subsequent scholarly assumptions about the nature of Epirote *politeia(i)* have been built. Cabanes' opinion on this specific matter leaned towards federalism. According to him, between c. 330 and 232 BC the Epirote *symmachia* was not a loose alliance of tribes under royal leadership, but a federal state with a monarchical head. Thus, alongside the king existed a second, permanent level of government, where decision-making took place.²⁵

In recent years, J.K. Davies²⁶ has examined for the first time all the sources on Epirote constitution(s) in an article, in which he highlights a few documents, such as the *theorodokoi* lists of Epidaurus and Argos and a few new oracular tablets from Dodona, for which he provides full bibliographical references and an English translation. Although he does not advance any hypothesis on the *politeia* of the Molossians, he raises some fundamental issues, such as the real significance of the ethnics found in the inscriptions: do they reveal the presence of non-Molossian constituents, holding offices, within the Molossian polity? Do the ethnics –never mentioned twice– reflect real political-administrative processes? And moreover, why do epigraphic texts concern only individuals? Why do we lack treaties and public accounts?

²² N.G.L. HAMMOND, *Epirus: the Geography, the Ancient Remains, the History and Topography of Epirus and Adjacent Areas*, Oxford, 1967, p. 525-551 (mainly manumissions, grants of citizenship, Epirote tribes coinages).

²³ HAMMOND, *op. cit.*, p. 525-671; N.G.L. HAMMOND, "The *Koina* in Epirus and Macedonia", *ICL XVI* (1991), p. 183-192; N.G.L. HAMMOND, "The *Ethne* in Epirus and Upper Macedonia", *ABSA XCV* (2000), pp. 345-352.

²⁴ CABANES, *op. cit.*, p. 534-592.

²⁵ CABANES, *op. cit.*, p. 111-195; P. CABANES, "Problèmes de géographie administrative et politique dans l'Épire du IV^e siècle avant J.-C.", in *La Géographie administrative et politique d'Alexander à Mahomet. Actes du colloque de Strasbourg, 14-16 juin 1979*, Leiden, 1981, p. 19-38; P. CABANES, "Institutions politiques et développement urbain (IV^e – III^e s. avant J.-C.): réflexions historiques à partir de l'Épire", in C. ANTONETTI (a cura di), *Lo spazio ionico e le comunità della Grecia nord-occidentale. Territorio, società, istituzioni. Atti del Convegno Internazionale, Venezia 7-9 gennaio 2010*, Pisa, 2010, p. 117-137.

²⁶ DAVIES, *art. cit.*

Among the scholars who have pondered the nature of Epirote *politeia(i)*, relying to different extents on the dating of documents advanced by Evangelides, Franke, Hammond and Cabanes, E. Lepore²⁷ occupies a privileged place. He was the first to attempt a comprehensive synthesis of the history of Epirus up to the death of Alketas I. Although Lepore does not treat the crucial years of the passage from the *koinon* of the Molossians to the *symmachia* of the Molossians and of the Epirotes (his work ends in *c.* 370 BC), in making several *en passant* references to an Epirote federalism he does seem to consider Epirus as a federal state from the end of the 4th century BC onwards.²⁸

More recently the hypothesis of an Epirote federalism, grounded on literary evidence –mainly Diodorus’ and Plutarch’s accounts²⁹– and *theorodokoi* lists from Epidauros and Argos,³⁰ was embraced by S. Funke, G. Di Leo and P. Siewert.³¹ Funke, more forcefully than others, affirms that Apeiros was the official name of the Epirote state, a “monarchischer Bundesstaat”, from *c.* 330 up to 232 BC according to the *theorodokoi* list of Argos.³²

A slightly different opinion was expressed by J.A.O. Larsen³³ in his survey of all the Greek federal states, by claiming that Epirus was a “state combining monarchy, federalism and tribal organization” and “developed into what might be called an ethnic or tribal sympolity under a constitutional monarchy” because of the extension of the power of the Molossians from the 4th century onwards. According to Larsen, the Molossians lead first a Molossian confederacy that later incorporates a wider Epirote coalition. Such an expansion is attested in his opinion by the presence of the ethnic Omphales, clearly from the city of Omphaleon in Chaonia, listed among the Molossians, in 342-330/329 BC.³⁴

A step further in this complex debate has been made recently by Elizabeth A. Meyer, whose work deserves special attention here.³⁵ Meyer’s attempt to define the

²⁷ E. LEPORE, *Ricerche sull’antico Epiro. Le origini storiche e gli interessi greci*, Napoli, 1962.

²⁸ LEPORE, *op. cit.*, p. 164-165.

²⁹ PLUT., *Pyrrh.* V, 5; DIOD., XIX, 36 and 88.

³⁰ *IG IV*² 1, 95 and *SEG LVIII*, 321.

³¹ S. FUNKE, “Ἀπειρος 317-272 BC: the Struggle of the Diadochi and the Political Structure of the Federation”, in L. MOOREN (ed.), *Politics, Administration and Society in the Hellenistic and Roman World. Proceedings of the International Colloquium, Bertinoro 19-24 July 1997*, Leiden, 2000, p. 107-121; S. FUNKE, *Aiakidenmythos und epirotisches Königtum: der Weg einer hellenischen Monarchie*, Stuttgart, 2000; G. DI LEO, “Monarchia e statualità in Epiro prima della conquista romana”, in C. BEARZOT, F. LANDUCCI & G. ZECCHINI (a cura di), *Gli stati territoriali nel mondo antico*, Milano, 2003, p. 226-231; P. SIEWERT, “Il federalismo nel mondo greco fino al 338 a.C.”, in G. ZECCHINI (a cura di), *Il federalismo nel mondo antico*, Milano, 2005, p. 22-23.

³² FUNKE, *op. cit.*

³³ J.A.O. LARSEN, *Greek Federal States, their Institutions and History*, Oxford, 1968, p. 274-275.

³⁴ *SGDI II* 1334 and 1335.

³⁵ E.A. MEYER, *The Inscriptions of Dodona and a New History of Molossia*, Stuttgart, 2013.

politeia(i) of the Epirotes starts from interrogating a basic issue taken for granted by previous modern scholarship³⁶: is the dating of the honorary and manumission decrees from Dodona, which forms the basis of any argumentation on Epirote *politeia(i)*, correct? Meyer's enquiry stems from this simple question, but the results are ground-breaking, since she offers a new, stimulating and, to a large extent, revolutionary approach to the topic. Through a substantial re-dating of most of the epigraphic evidence concerning the *koinon* of the Molossians, the *symmachia* of the Epirotes and the other Epirote tribes, Meyer defines the political development of Molossia and Epirus with extreme coherence and accuracy.

In the first chapter (p. 13-17) Meyer briefly outlines "the established view", by giving reference to some, but not all, hypotheses, so far considered as the orthodoxy on the nature of Molossian and Epirote *politeiai*, and sketches the canonical three phases of the political development of Epirus: the Molossian *koinon* (c. 400-330/328 BC); the Epirote alliance or *symmachia* (c. 330/328-232 BC); and the Epirote *koinon* (232-167 BC). The result is rather schematic; more emphasis on the debate would have helped those who are not familiar with the history of Epirus.

In the second chapter (p. 18-45) Meyer starts deconstructing "the established view", by fixing the dating criteria of the major sources, i.e. manumission and honorary decrees found at Dodona. Meyer writes that the epigraphic evidence has "never been examined closely and the attribution of certain letter-forms to a certain century never systematically justified for this area or questioned" (p. 18). She sets up precise, but not strict, parameters of dating, which she calls the strong and weak criteria. Strong criteria are internal dating formulas, such as the names of kings, officials, etc.; weak criteria are letter-forms. While her reasoning on the dating of inscriptions on historical grounds is persuasive, for example her discussion on whether the Molossian king was Alexander II or Alexander I (p. 82-90), it is more difficult to argue for or against her technical arguments since they depend entirely on her autoptic examination. Meyer is aware that the use of letter forms alone is one of the "never entirely straightforward methods of dating", because of the media used to inscribe public documents at Dodona. The preference for metal plaques, mainly bronze and copper, on which "the fineness of the implement used to inscribe and the thickness of the metal bronze-inscribing produce different letters from contemporary stone-inscribing", multiplies the problems in creating a relative chronology of North-Western letter shapes (p. 19-20).

Such a re-consideration of the dating norms entails a significant change in the chronology of more than half of the whole cluster of inscriptions testifying to political change in Epirus in the late classical and Hellenistic periods. According to Meyer, fourteen of the twenty-seven texts should date to the 3rd century BC rather than to the 4th. As a consequence, the whole internal history of Epirus, the relationships between the *ethne* of Thesprotians, Chaonians and Molossians and the canonical tripartite sequence of Epirote constitutional development, should be rethought *in toto*. Two useful charts (p. 39-44), synthetically reporting grids with the letter shapes of Epirote

³⁶ Some doubt about the datings already arose in DAVIES, *art. cit.*, p. 246.

documents dating between 370 and 232 BC and a synopsis comparing Cabanes and others' dating with Meyer's, complete the chapter.

The third chapter (p. 46-113) concerns seven interrelated aspects in the history of Molossia, now reconsidered in light of the new datings: the nature of the Molossian "state" in the 4th century BC; the (alleged) Molossian expansion in the 4th century BC; the actual foundation of the new "state" in 330-328 BC; Epirote and Molossian identity in the late 4th – early 3rd centuries; the growth of the Molossian *koinon* in the 3rd century BC; the relationship between the *ethnos* of the Molossians and its neighbours, namely that between the Thesprotians and Molossians in the 3rd century BC. According to the new dating advanced by Meyer, there is no definite piece of evidence to support the existence of an entity known as the *koinon* of the Molossians in the 4th century BC (p. 47).

Her analysis aims at undermining the idea that the territorial expansion of Molossia in the late classical period is to be linked to the construction of the first federal state in Epirus. More specifically, Meyer tries to demonstrate, firstly, the reduced, or even non-existent, territorial expansion of the Molossian state in the 4th century BC and, secondly, the presence of an enduring monarchy in Molossia, overlooking the sanctuary of Dodona, along with an amphictyony administering the shrine. In particular, according to Meyer, the existence of an amphictyony at Dodona is suggested by the mention of the office of *damiourgoi*, who are not to be considered the representatives of tribes in a federal state, as they have been to date, but as magistrates of a board overseeing juridical and religious matters like at other sanctuaries. A persuasive parallel is Delphi, along with other shrines (p. 50-56). Against the territorial expansion of Molossia in the 4th century BC (p. 60-64), Meyer discusses a passage of Xenophon, according to which in 374/3 BC King Alketas helped six-hundred Athenian peltasts to pass from the Epirote mainland to the island of Corcyra.³⁷ Such a Molossian intervention should not be interpreted as a sign of territorial growth along the coast facing Corcyra in the 4th century BC. Meyer, indeed, affirms firmly that, in any case, "permission to pass through a territory to help a covert (and nocturnal) operation, and political (and military) domination of that territory, are not the same thing" (p. 61) and, moreover, "what little the Molossians achieved in the fourth century they could have achieved under virtually any form of government" (p. 63). She goes on saying that, even in the case of a territorial expansion of Molossia, there is insufficient proof to connect it with the formation of the federal *koinon* of the Molossians already in the 4th century BC. More likely, Molossia was reigned by kings in the 5th as well as in the 4th centuries BC. Such a picture is not in contrast with the prominent position occupied by the Molossians in North-Western Greece,³⁸ becoming from the first half of the 4th century BC onwards allied with their neighbours during conflicts, as well as the privileged partner in the foreign policies of

³⁷ XEN., *Hell.* VI, 2, 10.

³⁸ STRABO, VII, 7, 5; see M. MELFI & J. PICCININI, "Geografia storica del territorio di Hadrianopolis nella valle del Drino (V sec. a.C. – 44 a.C.)", in R. PERNA & Dh. ÇONDI (a cura di), *Hadrianopolis II. Risultati delle indagini archeologiche 2005-2010*, Bari, 2012, p. 38-40.

Syracuse and Athens during the 4th century,³⁹ and the first promoters of the monumental blooming at the shrine of Dodona between the 4th and 3rd century BC.⁴⁰

The fourth chapter is the rewritten history of Molossia (p. 114-135), according to epigraphic evidence examined previously, i.e. non-oracular inscriptions found at Dodona from the 5th century BC until 232 BC, that is to say until the appearance of the Epirote *koinon*, the first “genuine federation”, in Meyer’s words (p. 126). The Molossian royal family ruled continuously, apart from a short Macedonian interlude, over its territory until 232 BC, and co-administered the shrine of Dodona with an amphictyony of largely local composition. The political relationships between the Molossians and the neighbouring *ethne* until the constitution of the *symmachia* of the Epirotes in the late 3rd century BC were not characterized, then, by total domination: Thesprotians and Chaonians were not incorporated into a wider Epirote “state”, but rather tied together by a hegemonic alliance, where the Molossians were the leaders over other “independent” groups, as in part already suggested by Davies.⁴¹

The last part of the book is an epigraphic appendix (p. 136-165) of manumission inscriptions from Dodona (nos. 1-27), Gitana (nos. 28-29) and Phoinike (nos. 30-31), listed according to Meyer’s new datings. For each inscription Meyer offers the Greek text, an English translation, a complete bibliography and either a drawing or a black-and-white picture. The volume concludes with useful indices of literary and epigraphic sources, a list of Greek names and a subject-index.

The book’s most evident limitation, perhaps due to space constraints, is the use of abbreviations instead of full epigraphic texts in the main discussion. In treating the epigraphic evidence Meyer uses *SGDI* numbers or Cabanes references –his Epigraphic appendix⁴²–, e.g. C(abanes) 6, to mention the inscriptions without reporting the text. Bold numbers in the main text refer to those manumission decrees inserted in her epigraphic appendix at the end of the volume. Such a method, admittedly stated in a footnote at the beginning of the book (p. 18 n. 26), burdens the reader. Indeed, the reader is compelled to look repeatedly at the end of the book, not always nor easily finding the desired pieces of evidence, or is expected to know by heart all *SGDI* and Cabanes’ inscriptions or else to have printed copies of these texts to hand.

Despite this inconvenience, this is an important book. Any modern study on the history of Molossia and Epirus has accepted the authority of older scholarship (mainly Cabanes and Hammond) without question. Meyer, on the contrary, has placed all the available evidence under scrutiny as well as its interpretation, also in terms of chronology. She, then, offers a convincing and more coherent systematization of the

³⁹ *IG* II² 45, l. 109-110; P.J. RHODES & R. OSBORNE, *Greek Historical Inscriptions, 404 – 323 B.C.*, Oxford, 2003, no. 33-34, 79; G. VANOTTI, “Alceta, Siracusa, Atene”, in *Hesperia* 7 (1996), p. 77-90.

⁴⁰ J. PICCININI, “Renaissance or Decline? The Shrine of Dodona in the Hellenistic and Early Roman Period”, in M. MELFI & O. BOBOU (eds.), *Hellenistic Sanctuaries. Between Greece and Rome*, Oxford (in print).

⁴¹ DAVIES, *art. cit.*, p. 234-258.

⁴² CABANES, *op. cit.*, p. 534-592.

epigraphic documents, which fits perfectly both with the growing political importance of the region and with the development of its major shrine, Dodona.

Institut für Römisches Recht und Antike Rechtsgeschichte Jessica PICCININI
Universität Wien